

Flares Aggregated Over 27-Day Solar Rotation Periods

Number of positive days per 27-days

25
20
15
10
5
0

Sunspot Number (average)
250
200
150
100
50
0

1996 2000 2004 2008 2012 2016 2020 2024

Date (start of 27-day period)

